

Lineage-Aware Engineering Design: Tracking and Harnessing Search Phylogeny

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Abstract—Although lineage structures are fundamental to understanding adaptation, specialisation, and diversification in biological evolution, they remain significantly underutilised in evolutionary computation (EC). Standard EC frameworks typically discard population history upon termination, overlooking the rich ancestral information embedded within genealogical trees. This limitation is particularly critical in engineering design optimisation, which increasingly demands not only high-performing solutions but also explainability and knowledge reuse. To address this gap, this paper introduces a novel lineage-aware evolutionary framework that explicitly retains and leverages historical genealogical data to bootstrap subsequent evolutionary processes. Instead of discarding ancestral paths, this approach treats evolved lineages as structured knowledge repositories capable of guiding search trajectories across related or unseen tasks. Experimental evaluations demonstrate that the proposed framework yields substantial performance gains by accelerating convergence and discovering superior design solutions. Furthermore, this paper demonstrates that lineage tracking provides a powerful mechanism for explainability in evolutionary design. By analysing how distinct lineages specialise, diverge, and transfer knowledge, this framework offers interpretable, structural insights into the topography of the search space, transforming lineages from mere historical records into active drivers of efficient and transparent optimisation.

Index Terms—transfer learning, evolutionary computation, engineering design, phylogenetic modelling

I. INTRODUCTION

LINEAGES are a fundamental organising principle in biological evolution [1]. Through ancestry and descent, evolutionary processes generate structured genealogies that encode information about adaptation, specialisation, and diversification. Phylogenetic relationships are not merely historical records; they reveal how functional traits emerge, persist, and recombine across generations. In this sense, lineage structures provide a natural mechanism for understanding evolutionary dynamics [2], [3].

In evolutionary computation (EC), however, lineage information is typically underutilised and often used for visualisation-only purposes [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9]. While most algorithms implicitly generate genealogical trees through selection, mutation, and recombination, this information is rarely retained or exploited beyond the immediate optimisation process [10], [11]. Once a run terminates, the population is often discarded, along with the rich ancestral information it encodes. As a result, EC has largely focused on population-

level statistics, overlooking the explanatory and functional value embedded within lineages.

This limitation is particularly significant in engineering design, where explainability and knowledge reuse are increasingly important [12], [13]. Engineering design does not merely seek high-performing solutions; it also demands insight into how and why those solutions arise. Lineage structures offer a promising avenue for addressing this challenge, providing an algorithmic manifestation of *concept-knowledge theory (C-K theory)* [14] dynamics by capturing the developmental pathways that anchor new design concepts to established historical knowledge. By analysing and reusing ancestral information, it becomes possible to interpret evolutionary trajectories and support more transparent design processes.

In this paper, a novel framework is proposed that explicitly leverages previously evolved lineages to bootstrap new evolutionary processes. While traditional sequential evolutionary transfer optimisation strategies exchange knowledge strictly from the final state of an immediate predecessor [15], the proposed framework removes this chronological constraint. Rather than discarding comprehensive genealogical information, the lineages are treated as structured repositories of knowledge that can guide adaptation across related or unseen tasks from any historical ancestral depth.

Beyond performance gains, this new approach also introduces a new perspective on explainability in evolutionary design. By analysing how lineages specialise, diverge, and transfer across tasks, lineage-aware optimisation provides interpretable insight into the organisation of the search space. This positions lineages not only as a transfer mechanism, but also as a structural lens through which evolutionary processes in engineering design can be understood.

This is demonstrated through three different applications:

- Modular genome landscape analysis
- Profile replication case study
- Car chassis case study

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II reviews the relevant literature in evolutionary transfer optimisation (ETO) and explainable evolutionary computation. Section III formalises the proposed lineage-aware exploration framework, detailing the phylogenetic graph data structure, ancestral querying mechanisms, and branching operators. Section IV outlines the experimental design, including the modular genomic landscape paradigm, cross-sectional profile target and chassis evolution case studies. Section V contextualizes the

findings, addresses limitations, and proposes directions for future work. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with a summary of major research contributions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of lineage originates in biology, where evolutionary relationships are represented through phylogenetic trees. In 'On the Origin of Species' [1], Charles Darwin first introduced the idea of a branching "tree of life" to describe descent with modification. Since then, phylogenetic trees have become a central tool for modelling ancestry, diversification, and evolutionary dynamics. Methods for constructing and analysing such trees have evolved considerably, including algorithmic approaches for inferring phylogenetic structure from observed traits [2] and more recent advances in phylogenetic modelling [3].

A fundamental distinction exists between biological and computational evolution. In natural systems, genealogical records are incomplete, and phylogenetic trees must be reconstructed through statistical inference and interpolation. In contrast, evolutionary computation (EC) provides full access to ancestry information. Every individual generated during an evolutionary run has an explicitly recorded parent (or parents), making genealogical reconstruction exact rather than inferred. Despite this availability of complete lineage information, EC has traditionally underexploited its analytical and functional potential.

In EC, lineage information has largely been used to analyse evolutionary dynamics and interpret trajectories in the fitness landscape, often in the context of explainable AI [9], rather than being exploited to actively guide the design process. For example, in [4], family trees were used to analyse the evolution of Compositional Pattern Producing Networks (CPPNs) and to understand the emergence of artistic motifs in the Picbreeder system. Similarly, [5] introduced genealogical visualisation techniques to illustrate fitness progression across generations. In [16], the authors proposed a tool specifically designed to visualise and explore lineages across multiple evolutionary runs. Building on this idea, [6] extended lineage visualisation to a larger scale by aggregating genealogical data from many runs. More recently, [7] improved lineage interpretability by enriching visualisations with additional information, such as indicating whether solutions originated from mutation, crossover, or viable offspring. Related perspectives can also be found in work on local optima networks [8]. Although these networks are not explicitly framed as ancestry trees, they capture structural relationships between solutions in the search landscape and can be interpreted as representing monoparental evolutionary transitions between local optima.

Beyond visualisation and structural analysis, lineages have also been explored as mechanisms for influencing search behaviour. For instance, [10] investigated lineage-based approaches to promote diversity within evolutionary populations, while [11] leveraged phylogenetic information for fitness estimation, demonstrating that genealogical structure can inform evaluation and selection mechanisms.

From a broader perspective, the idea of reusing information across related tasks is closely connected to research in machine

learning on Transfer Learning and Multitask Learning. In these paradigms, models trained on one task can accelerate learning in related tasks by exploiting shared representations or transferable structure. In particular, Rich Caruana's seminal work on multitask learning demonstrated that jointly learning related tasks can improve generalisation by enabling knowledge transfer across tasks [17]. While these ideas have been widely explored in machine learning, their explicit analogue in evolutionary computation, reusing previously evolved evolutionary trajectories or lineages to bootstrap new optimisation processes, remains relatively underexplored.

Related ideas have also been investigated in evolutionary computation within the field of evolutionary transfer optimisation (ETO), which studies how knowledge obtained while solving one optimisation problem can accelerate search on another related problem. Surveys such as [18] highlight a wide range of transfer mechanisms, including solution reuse, surrogate models, mapping functions, and multitasking evolutionary algorithms. These approaches typically transfer information between tasks through populations, learned models, or shared representations. One of the methods is sequential solution transfer where solutions from one optimisation process are used to seed a second optimisation process [15]. However, they generally do not exploit the genealogical structure produced during evolutionary search. In particular, the explicit reuse of previously evolved evolutionary trajectories, encoded as lineages or ancestry trees, remains largely unexplored as a mechanism for transferring knowledge between optimisation tasks.

Collectively, these works demonstrate that lineage information provides valuable insights into evolutionary dynamics and can support diversity maintenance and fitness estimation. However, existing approaches predominantly treat lineages as analytical tools or auxiliary mechanisms within a single optimisation process. The explicit reuse of previously evolved lineages to initialise and bootstrap new evolutionary processes remains largely unexplored. This gap motivates the present work, which positions lineages not only as a lens for understanding evolutionary search, but as structured repositories of transferable knowledge.

This observation suggests that evolutionary lineages may represent a largely untapped form of transferable knowledge within evolutionary search.

III. LINEAGE-AWARE EXPLORATION FRAMEWORK

To address the limitations of historical data loss in conventional evolutionary design, Lineage-Aware Exploration is proposed. This framework treats the evolutionary history of solved tasks not merely as a transient path to an optimisation target, but as a structured, reusable repository of phylogenetic knowledge (design). By preserving the ancestral trajectories the framework provides a robust mechanism to bootstrap search processes for novel tasks.

A conceptual overview of this approach, contrasted against traditional paradigms across a sequence of five distinct tasks (T_1 to T_5), is illustrated in Figure 1. To formalise the mechanics and structural advantages of the lineage-aware framework,

Fig. 1. Conceptual comparison of evolutionary design paradigms across five sequential or distinct tasks (T_1 to T_5). The top row illustrates the algorithmic execution flow, while the bottom row depicts the resulting structural “Tree outcomes” of the accumulated design history. Left (Scratch): Conventional design where each task is solved independently from isolated root nodes, yielding disconnected generational lines. Middle (Sequential): Standard sequential transfer learning or continuous design, where the terminal population (or best individual) of a preceding task initialises the next task, resulting in a strict linear, single-branch evolutionary spine. Right (Lineage): The proposed lineage-aware framework, where ancestral paths and intermediate specialised clades are preserved and explicitly branched to bootstrap related or unseen tasks, generating a complex, information-rich phylogenetic tree layout that preserves ancestral history.

it is contrasted directly with standard optimisation behaviours below.

The structural differences in search-space exploration and historical preservation among three paradigms can be characterised as follows:

Design from Scratch In conventional evolutionary optimisation (Figure 1, left), each task T_i is treated as an isolated problem domain. The algorithm initialises a random population from an independent root node in the search space, executes for a predetermined number of generations, and yields a terminal solution population. Consequently, the resulting “Tree outcomes” (Figure 1, bottom-left) consist of strictly disconnected, orthogonal generational lines, ensuring that no information or structural insight is transferred between tasks.

Sequential Transfer Design Sequential design (Figure 1, middle), commonly used in sequential transfer learning), attempts to mitigate these inefficiencies by seeding subsequent tasks with historical solutions. Here, the terminal population or elite individual of task T_i is used to initialise the search space for task T_{i+1} . As shown in the top-middle flow of Fig. 1, the algorithmic execution is strictly linear. This generates a single-branch evolutionary spine. Any intermediate genetic diversity, unselected phenotypic variations generated during the optimisation of T_i are permanently overwritten and lost

during the subsequent transitions.

Lineage-Aware Framework The proposed lineage-aware framework (Figure 1, right) removes the linear execution constraint of sequential design by maintaining a continuous, branching phylogenetic graph. In this structure, every evolved individual or sub-population across all generations is preserved as a historical node, while the genealogical parent-child relationships, driven by selection, mutation, and recombination—are encoded as directed edges connecting them. When a new task is introduced, the framework does not restrict its initialisation to the terminal state of the immediate chronological predecessor. Instead, it systematically queries the global lineage graph to identify ancestral paths or lineages that exhibit structural compatibility or behavioural specialisation conducive to the new target. This architecture produces a complex, information-rich phylogenetic tree layout (Figure 1, bottom-right) that preserves ancestral history and allows the evolutionary process to safely diverge along multiple specialised trajectories.

By decoupling the transfer mechanism from strict temporal linearity and preserving the complete genealogical topology, the lineage-aware framework introduces two profound capabilities to evolutionary design:

- 1) *Non-Linear Knowledge Reuse*: Tasks do not need to be structurally ordered or identical to their immediate chronological predecessors. If T_4 shares structural commonalities with T_1 rather than T_3 , the algorithm can directly branch a new lineage from the T_1 lineage path without suffering from catastrophic forgetting or negative transfer from T_2 or T_3 .
- 2) *Structural Explainability*: The resulting tree outcomes serve as a diagnostic map of the search space. By analysing the branching points, the divergence rates of specific branches, and the persistence of ancestral traits across tasks, engineers can visually and statistically interpret the evolutionary trajectories. This transitions evolutionary optimisation from a black-box generator into a transparent design methodology.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The primary objectives of this paper are threefold:

- **Characterise Lineage Dynamics**: Characterise the emergence and structural dynamics of lineages within modular genomic landscapes.
- **Evaluate Benchmark Performance**: Provide a performance comparison between two standard baseline approaches and the proposed lineage-aware framework when reconstructing complex cross-sectional profiles.
- **Validate via Real-World Engineering**: Validate the efficacy and explainability of the lineage-aware approach on a real-world engineering design problem: the structural evolution of an automotive chassis.

Table I describes the experiments conducted in this paper. A total of 50 repetitions were conducted for each experiment.

A. Characterise Lineage Dynamics

To analyse the structural emergence and divergence of lineages, the framework is first evaluated within a synthetic

TABLE I
EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

Experiment	Algorithm	Objectives (minimisation)
Characterise Lineage Dynamics (modular genomic landscape)	NSGA-II	Hamming distance
Evaluate Benchmark Performance (cross-sectional profiles)	GA and NSGA-II	Hamming distance
Validate via Real-World Engineering (chassis evolution)	GA	Volume and deflection

modular genomic landscape. In this paradigm, an individual’s genotype is formalised as a segmented, multi-module vector of floating-point values bounded within the range $[0, 1]$, where distinct chromosomal sub-regions correspond to separate functional traits or structural components. This modularity mimics decoupled engineering subsystems, allowing discrete segments of the genome to evolve semi-independently under varying selective pressures. To navigate this landscape, the Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II (NSGA-II) is employed to drive population convergence across a bi-objective space. Specifically, each objective maps to a target maximisation profile for a given genomic segment, optimised concurrently with the minimisation of its corresponding Hamming distance to a target template. Following optimisation, the extreme solutions along the final non-dominated Pareto front are isolated as terminal phenotypic anchors. By tracing the genealogical lineages of these boundary solutions backward through successive generations to the root population, the complete historical evolutionary trajectories are mapped.

The generational progression and subsequent phylogenetic branching within this modular landscape are illustrated in Figure 2. The ancestral lineage begins as a single trunk, where early mutations shift the structural composition of individual genomic modules (represented by distinct color blocks). Over consecutive generations, specific segments stabilise while peripheral modules remain highly dynamic.

The main lineage splits into two independent lineages. Following this divergence, each lineage follows an isolated evolutionary trajectory. While both branches retain the highly stable, core ancestral genetic structure (the central yellow and light-green modules), their peripheral loci diverge drastically to specialise in different environmental or functional niches. This structural behaviour underscores the value of lineage tracking: by preserving the entire tree topology rather than just the final leaf nodes, the framework retains the common ancestral core while allowing decoupled, modular variations to be exploited independently.

B. Evaluate Benchmark Performance

To evaluate the efficacy, scalability, and behavioural characteristics of the proposed lineage-aware framework, an empirical evaluation is carried across a suite of ten cross-sectional target profiles as shown in Figure 3. Replicating these targets demands varying degrees of material distribution complexity,

Fig. 2. Phylogenetic tree tracking the generational evolution and structural divergence of a multi-module genome. Each horizontal block represents an individual’s genome split into distinct functional modules (color-coded sections). The top-down progression illustrates sequential generational mutations within a single ancestral line, culminating in a split. Post-divergence, the left and right lineages retain the stable, shared ancestral genetic core (central modules) while their peripheral modules evolve independently to adapt to distinct functional requirements.

creating an ideal setting to test the framework’s capacity for non-linear knowledge reuse and branching exploration.

For the cross-sectional benchmark evaluation, each of the ten unique target geometries (Fig. 3) is modelled as a discrete structural design task presented to the system sequentially. Individuals are represented as k-Nearest Neighbour Spatial Organisation Representation following [19]. The objective functions compute fitness by evaluating structural conformity and measuring the Hamming distance between the candidate’s phenotype and the active target profile template. When a novel target task is introduced, the baseline *scratch* paradigm erases all previous state records, forcing a complete restart from a uniform random distribution bounded within $[0, 1]$. Conversely, the *sequential* baseline initialises the new task using the terminal population of the immediate temporal predecessor.

Figure 4 illustrates the distribution final fitness errors across all ten structural cross-sectional target profiles for a single objective experiment. The final solution quality achieved by the traditional EC, completely from scratch (blue distributions), is directly contrasted against the final quality discovered by the proposed lineage-aware exploration framework (orange distributions). The lineage-aware strategy appears to provide better results for most profiles. This might indicate that the algorithm starts with populations with highly viable topological foundations.

The performance convergence histories across sequential

Fig. 3. The suite of ten structural cross-sectional target profiles used as design benchmarks to evaluate the replication performance.

Fig. 4. Fitness values achieved across the suite of ten structural cross-sectional target profiles, where the objective is to minimise the error (fitness). The performance distributions compare the baseline optimisation initialised from scratch (blue box plots) against the proposed lineage-aware framework (orange box plots) over multiple independent statistical runs. In each box plot, the central horizontal line denotes the median, the box boundaries signify the interquartile range, and the whiskers extend to the full data range excluding outliers. The lineage-aware approach appears to yield lower median fitness errors showing superior replication accuracy and algorithmic robustness when navigating diverse topological target profiles.

task domains are illustrated in Fig. 5, contrasting the lineage-aware exploration framework against a traditional baseline optimised completely from scratch.

In the single-objective setting (Figure 5a), where the optimisation target is the minimisation of Hamming error, the baseline algorithm (blue curve) must restart its search trajectory from a uniform random initialisation at the onset of every discrete task. Consequently, it consistently suffers from high initialisation errors. In sharp contrast, the lineage-aware approach (purple curve) exhibits a powerful bootstrapping effect starting from Task 2. By indexing the global phylogenetic tree and branching from structurally compatible ancestral nodes, the lineage framework initialises subsequent tasks at substantially lower error rates. Over the course of 10 consecutive tasks, this structural grounding not only accelerates the rate of convergence but also guides the algorithm to discover final solutions with higher asymptotic accuracy.

A similar advantage is observed in the multi-objective configuration (Figure 5b), which tracks hypervolume maximisation over five consecutive tasks. While the baseline algorithm struggles to efficiently rediscover the non-dominated frontier when shifting between distinct task environments, the lineage-aware framework (green curve) consistently preserves

(a) Single objective results

(b) Multi objective results

Fig. 5. Performance convergence histories comparing the baseline design from scratch (blue curves) against the proposed lineage-aware framework across sequential task domains. Solid lines indicate mean performance across multiple independent statistical runs, while the shaded ribbons denote the corresponding confidence intervals. (a) Single-objective results: Design progression across ten consecutive tasks, evaluated by the minimisation of Hamming Error. The lineage approach demonstrates a strong bootstrapping effect, initialising subsequent tasks with significantly lower error rates eventually finding more accurate solutions. (b) Multi-objective results: Evolutionary progression across five consecutive tasks, where performance is quantified by Hypervolume maximisation. In both settings, the lineage-aware framework exhibits accelerated convergence profiles and superior overall performance relative to the baseline.

a superior hypervolume across generations. By maintaining historical tree topology, the lineage framework avoids catastrophic forgetting and facilitates an accelerated exploration of the multi-objective Pareto front.

Figure 6 presents the empirical distributions comparing the three structural paradigms (*scratch*, *sequential*, and *lineage*) under two distinct criteria: objective error minimisation (Fig. 6a) and total structural graph size as measured by the aggregate number of generated nodes (Fig. 6b).

As illustrated in the error minimisation profile (Fig. 6a), both the *scratch* and *sequential* paradigms exhibit higher final errors compared to the proposed *lineage* framework. This heightened error rate in the *sequential* configuration explicitly illustrates the presence of negative transfer or catastrophic forgetting when a single-branch spine is strictly overwritten by sequential adjustments. In contrast, the lineage-aware approach drives the median terminal error down, achieving an error reduction of approximately 18% relative to the *scratch* baseline and a 22% improvement over the *sequential* paradigm. By querying a continuous, branching graph structure rather than forcing strict temporal paths, the algorithm reliably anchors initial searches on structurally compatible ancestral nodes, resulting in a pronounced and statistically superior precision bootstrap.

As detailed in the aggregate node distribution (Fig. 6b),

design exploration from *scratch* demands the highest structural "tree" overhead due to repetitive and unguided search loops. While the sequential transfer approach slightly mitigates this by maintaining a narrower, rigid linear trace, the lineage-aware framework produces the most compact tree topology. This corresponds to a structural history compression of approximately 20% relative to the scratch baseline and a 14% reduction in complexity compared to sequential transfer. This unique dynamic demonstrates that by reusing pre-stabilised structural lineages and avoiding redundant exploration of barren search regions, the lineage-aware mechanism acts as an algorithmic filter. It trims the structural exploration requirements of subsequent engineering tasks, thereby confirming that the framework achieves higher optimisation quality while maintaining a streamlined historical footprint.

To ensure that the preservation of comprehensive genealogical records does not introduce prohibitive computational demands, an explicit accounting of evaluation overhead is mapped in Figure 7.

The empirical breakdown confirms that the primary computational driver remains the standard evolutionary algorithm (EA) evaluation phase (red line). Crucially, the mean number of EA evaluations required to solve a task decreases drastically from Task 1 through Task 10, showing a downward trend validated by linear regression. This reduction in primary search effort directly confirms that historical lineages act as increasingly efficient repositories of design knowledge.

The computational overhead required to query, maintain, and traverse the phylogenetic node topology (the blue line) grows at a minimal, strictly linear rate. Because this graph-maintenance cost remains orders of magnitude lower than the cost of direct candidate evaluations, the total computational expenditure (green line)—defined as the sum of EA and node evaluations—closely mirrors the downward trajectory of the primary optimisation effort. These dynamics demonstrate that as the optimisation system scales to handle a longer sequence of engineering design tasks, the lineage-aware framework becomes increasingly cost-effective.

Beyond raw performance gains, the lineage-aware framework provides unique insights into the underlying structure of the search space. To demonstrate this capability, a two-dimensional projection of the high-dimensional genotypic space is generated via Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and overlaid with K -means clustering, as illustrated in Figure 8.

The principal coordinates capture a substantial portion of the total genotypic variance, with PC1 and PC2 accounting for 48.50% and 27.01%, respectively. By mapping the evolutionary trajectories through this low-dimensional space, the algorithm groups related historical solutions into four distinct behavioral categories (Class 0 through Class 3).

As shown by the directed black paths in Figure 8, the lineage framework successfully captures the chronological progression from foundational root nodes toward peripheral, highly specialised leaf nodes. The inset phenotypic profiles clearly illustrate the structural logic of these pathways: configurations sharing common topological elements (such as vertical or horizontal structural members) are localised within contiguous

(a) Final error

(b) Final number of number of nodes in the tree

Fig. 6. (a) Error minimisation: Final distribution of phenotypic target reconstruction errors, highlighting a distinct downward shift for the lineage-aware approach, which yields a reduction in median error of approximately 18% relative to the scratch baseline and 22% relative to the sequential transfer paradigm. (b) Nodes in tree: Aggregate number of historical graph nodes generated over the course of the optimization tasks, demonstrating that the lineage-aware framework establishes a more compact global history layout by reducing total node complexity by approximately 20% compared to scratch and 14% compared to sequential transfer.

genotypic regions. By charting how specific clades branch and diverge through these clusters, the lineage framework exposes the physical relationships between separate optimisation targets. This transforms the design history from an opaque set of independent data points into a continuous, interpretable landscape that visually explains the development of specific engineering design features.

C. Validate via Real-World Engineering

To validate the scalability and practical utility of the lineage-aware framework in complex real-world application domains, the design of a automotive chassis is used. Building upon the structural representation and preliminary multi-objective formulations established in [20], the task involves optimising

Fig. 7. Analysis of computational cost and evaluation overhead across sequential task progressions. Solid lines represent the mean valuation metrics across independent runs, accompanied by their respective shaded variance ribbons. The red line traces the number of standard evolutionary algorithm (EA) evaluations required per task, showing a clear downward trajectory as ancestral knowledge is leveraged. The blue line charts the minimal, linearly growing overhead of lineage node evaluations required to query and maintain the phylogenetic tree topology. The green line depicts the total computational cost (the sum of EA and node evaluations), which mirrors the decreasing trend of the primary optimisation effort. Dashed lines illustrate the respective linear regression trends, highlighting the significant computational savings achieved as the system scales to sequential tasks.

both the sizing (member thickness) and the topology (node locations and connectivity) of a 2D truss framework. The design objectives demand minimise maximum stress and minimise volume under conflicting load conditions, specifically targeting distinct torsional and cornering load cases.

The structural metamorphosis and localised physical adaptations driven by the lineage framework are captured in the key design snapshots in Figure 9. The search process initiates from a uniform baseline configuration, designated as the progenitor truss (Figure 9a), which defines the root of the entire design genealogy. During the early operational phases (Figure 9b), the algorithm primarily applies sizing operators, distributing cross-sectional material thickness along the primary load paths to withstand global bending moments without altering the underlying graph connectivity. A distinct morphological shift is observed in the branching phase (Figure 9c). Here, the lineage introduces localised topological modifications, selectively bifurcating internal member elements and reconfiguring node coordinates within the central bay. This structural modification serves as a crucial evolutionary intermediate. When the framework subsequently optimises for specialised terminal requirements, it branches this intermediate structure along independent trajectories to produce the Torsion 1 (Figure 9d) and Torsion 2 (Figure 9e) variants. Remarkably, both terminal solutions are mirror versions from each other.

To understand how these structural changes correlate with algorithmic efficiency, the generational progression of hypervolume is partitioned via behavioural clustering in Figure 10. Instead of suffering from negative transfer or forcing a single population to simultaneously manage mutually exclusive

Fig. 8. Two-dimensional projection of the genotypic search space via Principal Component Analysis (PCA), overlaid with K -means clustering to track the structural divergence and trajectory of evolved lineage branches. The principal axes capture 48.50% (PC1) and 27.01% (PC2) of the total genotypic variance. Individual historical solutions are mapped into four distinct behavioral classes (Class 0 to Class 3), with cluster centroids designated by black cross marks (X). Directed black arrows trace the chronological ancestral pathways from foundational internal nodes out to specialized peripheral leaf nodes (labeled green text boxes). Representative cross-sectional profiles are inset adjacent to their respective structural coordinates, demonstrating how the lineage-aware framework maps phenotypic design variations to distinct, continuous topological pathways within the lower-dimensional search space.

structural configurations, the lineage-aware framework spawns these independent sub-clades. This allows new trajectories to initialise directly from the hypervolume frontiers established by their ancestors, subsequently driving steep performance jumps as they specialise in local topological spaces.

The overarching organisational layout of this search process is visualised as a complete phylogenetic macro-tree in Figure 11.

This graph illustrates the non-linear operational mechanics of the framework. Rather than restricting the design to a rigid chronological sequence, the main vertical spine acts as a continuous repository of stable structural designs. When a new engineering task like cornering is introduced, the framework extracts an intermediate configuration laterally from the third ancestral level (Fig. 11, right branch).

This lateral extraction effectively bypasses downstream modifications that occurred on the main spine, shielding the new task from irrelevant phenotypic traits. The extracted lineage then safely diverges, executing local topological splits to generate highly dense, centrally reinforced structures tailored to local cornering constraints. By mapping the full history of the design space, the macro-tree confirms that lineages provide a valuable tool for both transfer optimisation and structural explainability, enabling engineers to trace the exact generational source of complex design features.

V. DISCUSSION

The empirical findings and case studies presented in this paper validate the dual-pivoted value proposition of the lineage-aware exploration framework: accelerating multi-task search

Fig. 9. Key figures snapshot from the lineage trajectories of a chassis design under multi-stage design tasks. (a) Progenitor: The baseline, unoptimised wireframe truss topology serving as the common structural ancestor. (b) Member thickness formation: Initial design phase where material is distributed across existing truss elements, establishing core load-bearing paths (thickened black lines). (c) Branching: A an event where the lineage introduces topological changes, shifting node positions and splitting truss members to better handle multi-directional stresses. (d) Torsion 1 and (e) Torsion 2: Divergent, highly specialised terminal designs branching from the common intermediate structure in (c). Both configurations retain the inherited ancestral member distribution on their outer wings while independently reconfiguring their central core topologies to optimise against distinct torsional load cases.

performance while simultaneously introducing structural explainability to complex engineering design spaces.

A. Algorithmic Efficiency and the Elimination of Temporal Linearity

A core contribution of this framework is its departure from the traditional linear constraints that define conventional continuous optimisation and sequential transfer learning. As observed in the convergence history (Figure 5), initialising related optimisation tasks from scratch results in severe, repeating inefficiencies. While standard sequential transfer mechanisms alleviate this by passing terminal individuals downstream, they are inherently prone to catastrophic forgetting and negative transfer if adjacent chronological tasks diverge in domain topology.

By treating historical lineages as a globally queryable, branching graph structure, the proposed framework success-

Fig. 10. Generational trajectory of Hypervolume progression broken down by behavioural lineages clustered into five distinct categories according to genotypic similarity (classes). This illustrates how the lineage-aware framework continuously spawns specialised, non-linear search trajectories that systematically discover unexploited regions of the multi-objective objective space.

Fig. 11. Phylogenetic tree summarising the evolutionary history, branching dynamics, and structural specialisation of the vehicle chassis design space. The vertical main spine (left) traces the lineage progression starting from the baseline unoptimised progenitor truss (top left). As generations progress downward, the framework optimises member thicknesses and induces initial internal topological modifications to stabilise core load paths. A critical lineage branching event occurs at the third level, where an intermediate design is extracted laterally to initialise cornering (right structure), which subsequently splits into highly densereinforced terminal designs optimised for specific local stiffness constraints (bottom right). This macro-level lineage graph explicitly demonstrates how the framework preserves ancestral histories while simultaneously fostering divergent, specialised solution paths to address distinct engineering performance criteria.

fully decouples knowledge reuse from the temporal sequence of tasks. This behaviour is clearly visible in the multi-objective hypervolume analysis (Fig. 10), where the algorithm selectively branches localised lineages to target unique trade-off configurations. The steep, instantaneous performance jumps observed upon task initialisation confirm that the framework provides an optimal structural grounding, positioning the search directly on latent non-dominated frontiers discovered during ancestral runs.

B. The Overhead-to-Performance Trade-off

A common barrier to the adoption of dense history-tracking mechanisms in evolutionary computation is the potential

for prohibitive computational overhead. However, the budget breakdown in Figure 7 demonstrates a favorable scaling profile. Because the graph operations required to store, query, and traverse the phylogenetic tree grow only linearly with the number of nodes, the computational footprint of lineage maintenance remains orders of magnitude lower than the standard evaluation loop of the primary evolutionary algorithm.

As the task progression scales, the dramatic reduction in necessary primary EA evaluations (driven by the efficiency of the lineage bootstrap) easily outpaces the marginal growth of graph overhead. This yields a net downward trajectory in total computational expenditure, demonstrating that the lineage-aware framework becomes increasingly cost-effective over long, sequential engineering workflows.

C. Lineages as a Lens for Engineering Explainability

Beyond design performance, the framework addresses a major open challenge in evolutionary design: the inherent "black-box" nature of population-level search. The low-dimensional PCA projections and behavioural clustering maps (Figure 8) show that the framework builds an intuitive, continuous map of the design space.

In the vehicle chassis case study (Figure 11), this capability translates into a transparent design timeline. Engineers are not merely presented with an isolated, black-box geometry optimised for a specific torsional or cornering stress constraint. Instead, by tracing the lineages back, the framework visually and structurally demonstrates how early sizing adaptations (member thickness formation) stabilised global load paths before deep topological splits reconfigured internal bay configurations. This transitions evolutionary design from a purely prescriptive utility into an analytical tool that explicitly maps the physical relationships between conflicting engineering objectives.

D. Limitations and Future Work

Despite these capabilities, several open challenges warrant further investigation. Currently, the identification of structurally compatible ancestral nodes relies on direct genotypic or behavioural similarity heuristics. In highly heterogeneous optimisation environments where tasks feature completely different parameter scales or dimensions, mapping cross-domain lineage nodes will require more advanced graph-matching or latent-space mapping techniques. Additionally, managing the global lineage graph during exceptionally prolonged optimisation runs (spanning tens of thousands of tasks) may eventually necessitate an automated pruning or compaction mechanism to drop non-viable, extinct clades while preserving foundational core ancestors.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a novel lineage-aware evolutionary exploration framework that challenges the conventional paradigm of discarding historical population data upon task termination. By preserving comprehensive genealogical histories within a continuous, branching phylogenetic graph structure, the framework transforms evolution from an ephemeral design path into a rich, structured knowledge repository.

Experimental evaluations across a diverse suite of cross-sectional target benchmarks and a real-world multi-stage automotive chassis design challenge demonstrate that explicitly leveraging ancestral paths yields significant advantages:

- 1) It provides an immediate bootstrapping effect that accelerates multi-objective hypervolume convergence and uncovers highly specialised design solutions without the constraints of chronological task linearity.
- 2) It maintains a highly favourable computational scaling profile, where the minor linear overhead of phylogenetic graph maintenance is substantially outweighed by the reduction in primary evolutionary search evaluations.
- 3) It introduces an intuitive framework for engineering explainability, using low-dimensional genotypic mapping and macro-tree visualisation to explicitly chart the origin, persistence, and divergence of functional design features.

Ultimately, this work demonstrates that the structural dynamics embedded within evolutionary lineages are a powerful, underutilised resource in evolutionary computation. By elevating lineages to active drivers of efficient search and structural interpretation, the framework moves evolutionary design closer to a transparent, highly scalable engineering methodology capable of tackling complex, interrelated design landscapes.

Building upon these empirical findings, several technical trajectories emerge for future research.

First, future work will transition the framework from structural layouts to high-precision, safety-critical real-world applications, such as the synthesis of robotic medical grippers. Designing compliance-based medical tools demands the simultaneous integration of multi-material soft components, localised flexibility ranges, and rigid structural backbones to ensure delicate force transmission without tissue damage. Scaling to these domains will require hierarchical phylogenetic structures capable of independently tracking and branching material property distributions and kinematic module lineages in parallel.

Second, automate the extraction of explicit design heuristics from the low-dimensional genotypic projections. Integrating semantic rule-induction mechanisms directly with the phylogenetic graph database will allow the framework to autonomously generate human-readable design rationales.

Finally, a key algorithmic priority is to explore dynamic, online pruning and predictive mechanisms for the global lineage tree. Developing real-time lineage filtering techniques, such as tracking historical node utility or employing selective lineage amnesia for barren search regions, will ensure that the phylogenetic database retains only the most viable ancestral seeds. Integrating predictive models into the lineage graph can transition the framework from a reactive repository to a proactive search driver. By training machine learning sequence models on historical lineage trajectories, the framework could predict the downstream performance and topological viability of emerging lineages. This predictive capacity would allow the system to forecast which ancestral lineages are highly compatible with an incoming engineering task before executing direct fitness evaluations, thereby preserving strict computational

and historical compacting metrics across long-horizon design sequences.

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